

Sensing in the next generation of wireless communications: The MultiX approach

Pablo Picazo-Martínez⁽¹⁾, Antonio de la Oliva⁽¹⁾
papicazo@pa.uc3m.es, aoliva@it.uc3m.es ⁽¹⁾
Dpto. de Telemática, Universidad Carlos III de Madrid

Resumen—Resumen—Next-generation wireless networks will integrate sensing and communication, enabling intelligent and perception-driven connectivity. The MultiX approach introduces the MultiX Fusion Perceptive 6G-RAN (MP6R), a framework that leverages multi-band, multi-static, multi-sensor, and multi-technology capabilities to enhance situational awareness and network adaptability. To address network heterogeneity, MultiX proposes a distributed architecture comprising the MultiX Perception System (MPS) for embedded sensing, the MP6R Controller (MP6RC) for network orchestration, and the Data Access and Security Hub (DASH) for secure multi-sensor data processing. As a proof of concept, we present the Multi-Layer Digital Twin for Industrial Manufacturing, demonstrating how contextual data optimizes decision-making and real-time network adaptation. By integrating sensing across the RAN, MultiX transforms wireless networks into active perception platforms, supporting applications such as autonomous systems, smart manufacturing, and environment-aware wireless optimization, paving the way for future 6G networks.

I. INTRODUCTION

Sensing is becoming a fundamental component of next-generation wireless communication systems, enabling devices to perceive and interpret their surroundings. By leveraging wireless signals, modern sensing techniques can detect motion, map environments, and track objects without requiring dedicated sensors. This capability is especially relevant for applications such as autonomous systems, smart environments, and human-computer interaction (see Fig. 1).

Future wireless networks will not only facilitate communication but also integrate advanced sensing paradigms. Multi-RAT (Radio Access Technology) sensing allows seamless operation across different wireless standards, such as 5G, Wi-Fi, and beyond, leveraging their unique strengths for robust perception. In addition, multiband sensing exploits diverse frequency ranges, combining sub-6 GHz for wide coverage with millimeter-wave (mmWave) and terahertz (THz) [1] bands for high-resolution sensing.

By integrating these approaches, next-generation wireless systems can achieve a more comprehensive and adaptive sensing framework, supporting applications like smart cities, vehicular networks, and industrial automation [2]. This convergence of communication and sensing marks a paradigm shift, pushing wireless networks beyond data transmission toward a more intelligent and context-aware future.

II. MAIN CHALLENGES ON SENSING

Most Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) research focuses on a single wireless technology [3]–[5], either within 3GPP-based networks (e.g., 5G/6G) or non-3GPP standards (e.g., IEEE 802.11 Wi-Fi sensing). While these studies

Fig. 1. The MultiX project, overview of use cases

demonstrate promising results, they often operate independently, limiting their potential in heterogeneous environments. Meanwhile, traditional sensing relies on dedicated sensors such as LiDAR, cameras, and radars, which remain separate from wireless communication, leading to redundant hardware and spectrum usage.

The key challenge for ISAC lies in managing network heterogeneity and integrating diverse sensing sources and ISAC technologies across the entire Radio Access Network (RAN), from the infrastructure to the User Equipment (UE) [6]. This requires addressing differences in frequency bands, waveforms, and hardware capabilities while ensuring seamless coordination across different layers of the RAN stack.

A unified ISAC framework must enable efficient spectrum sharing, real-time signal processing, and cross-layer data fusion without degrading communication performance. AI-driven sensing [7], [8], edge computing [9], and dynamic resource allocation [10] will be crucial for overcoming interoperability challenges. A fully integrated ISAC system would transform wireless networks into perception-aware infrastructures, supporting applications such as precise indoor localization, crop tracking, environmental disaster tracking, and robotic autonomous system coordination 1.

III. MULTIX VISION

The MultiX project [11] aims to redefine the 3GPP RAN system by developing the MultiX Fusion Perceptive 6G-RAN (MP6R), which integrates advanced sensing and communication capabilities. MP6R leverages multiple dimensions of network intelligence to enable high-precision environmental perception and enhanced wireless performance.

Key aspects of MP6R (see Fig. 2) include:

- **Multi-Sensor Fusion:** MP6R integrates various sensing modalities to improve situational awareness and environmental mapping. Network-based sensing utilizes radio signals for passive and active detection, while radar,

Fig. 2. MultiX vision building blocks, considering different sensing modulations and technologies

LiDAR, and cameras provide complementary depth and motion data for enhanced object tracking.

- **Multi-Band Operation:** The system operates across a broad frequency spectrum, combining sub-6 GHz for wide-area coverage, mmWave and THz bands for high-resolution imaging and fine-grained localization, and emerging 7-24 GHz frequencies for a balanced trade-off between range and resolution.
- **Multi-Static Processing:** Signals transmitted by one or multiple network nodes are received and processed by distributed receivers, enabling collaborative sensing. This enhances passive detection, distributed radar-like perception, and network-assisted object tracking through fusion of signals across multiple receivers.
- **Multi-Technology Integration:** MP6R seamlessly combines 3GPP and non-3GPP technologies to extend sensing and communication capabilities. It utilizes 5G/6G cellular networks for joint communication and sensing while incorporating Wi-Fi and other technologies, ensuring interoperability across diverse environments.

By combining these principles, MP6R enables an intelligent, perception-driven wireless network that enhances localization, environmental sensing, and network adaptability.

IV. MULTIX ARCHITECTURE

The MultiX system introduces a novel architectural framework based on MP6R (see Fig. 3), which is designed to seamlessly integrate sensing and communication within the 6G Radio Access Network (RAN). By leveraging multi-band, multi-static, multi-sensor, and multi-technology deployments, MultiX enables a perception-driven wireless network that extends beyond traditional connectivity. The architecture is structured around three key components:

A. MultiX Perception System (MPS):

The MPS is responsible for embedding MultiX sensing functions across different layers of the RAN stack. These functions can be deployed at the Radio Unit (RU), Distributed Unit (DU), a fully-fledged Base Station (BS), and even at the User Equipment (UE) level. MPS enables joint signal processing across network elements, supporting advanced sensing features such as passive radar-like perception, fine-grained localization, and environmental awareness. By integrating sensing capabilities at various RAN nodes, MPS ensures that MultiX can operate in a distributed and flexible manner, optimizing performance across diverse deployment scenarios.

B. MP6R Controller (MP6RC):

Serving as the central intelligence of the MultiX Fusion Perceptive 6G-RAN (MP6R), the MP6RC is responsible for managing and orchestrating sensing and communication functionalities throughout the RAN. The controller performs two primary roles:

1. **Multi-Technology Coordination:** MP6RC oversees the integration of different wireless technologies (e.g., 5G, 6G, Wi-Fi, or non-terrestrial networks) while managing the mobility of sensing targets within the network. This ensures seamless operation across heterogeneous environments, enabling uninterrupted sensing and communication services.
2. **Distributed Data Management:** The MP6RC interfaces with and controls the Data Access and Security Hub (DASH) nodes across the RAN. Through this coordination, it ensures efficient multi-sensor data aggregation, processing, and sharing while maintaining network scalability and real-time responsiveness.

Fig. 3. MultiX architecture: enabling multi-band, multi-static, multi-sensor and multi-technology sensing

Fig. 4. Data Access and Security Hub main blocks

C. Data Access and Security Hub (DASH):

DASH (see Fig.4) is a novel RAN data plane entity designed to handle the aggregation, processing, and secure exposure of multi-sensor data across the network. It serves as a trusted hub for managing sensing information from diverse technologies, ensuring data privacy, security, and integrity. DASH can be fully distributed across the data plane, allowing flexible deployment wherever needed to optimize performance and latency. Key functionalities include:

- Secure storage and access control for multi-sensor data, ensuring trustworthiness and regulatory compliance.
- Efficient processing and fusion of heterogeneous sensing data, enabling improved perception and decision-making.
- Dynamic exposure of processed sensing information to authorized network functions, applications, and external services.

By combining these three core components, the MultiX

architecture creates a highly adaptive and intelligent RAN system, where sensing and communication are deeply intertwined. This enables next-generation applications such as ultra-precise localization, environment-aware wireless optimization, and autonomous network management, transforming the RAN into an active perception engine for 6G and beyond.

V. MULTIX PROOF OF CONCEPT

We will validate the MultiX architecture through a proof of concept called **Multi-Layer Digital Twin for Industrial Manufacturing** (see Fig. 5). This proof of concept aims to demonstrate how a Digital Twin (DT) platform can transform industrial manufacturing by integrating sensing, communication, and intelligent decision-making into a cohesive system. The DT serves as a virtual representation of real-world elements, continuously collecting and processing contextual information to improve decision-making, proactively resolve potential issues, and dynamically optimize configurations based on predicted events. This results in increased operational efficiency, precision, and reliability across industrial environments.

One of the key innovations of this DT is its ability to adjust wireless network services in real time, responding to the highly dynamic and challenging industrial radio environment. By enabling proactive adaptation, the platform ensures deterministic network behavior, guaranteeing performance for critical industrial applications. This capability is essential for achieving seamless connectivity and automation in industrial settings. The DT also fosters new forms of human-machine collaboration, leveraging autonomous technologies to enhance productivity and introduce novel business models that drive economic and social value.

Fig. 5. Proof of concept schematic scenario: Multi-Layer Digital Twin for Industrial Manufacturing

The DT is structured as a multi-layered and potentially distributed system, with its core component, DASH, acting as a hub for aggregating and processing contextual data from multiple sources, including networks, applications, and the surrounding industrial environment. It integrates ISAC and other discrete sensors, utilizing rule-based algorithms, simulations, and advanced machine-learning techniques to process vast amounts of heterogeneous data. These insights are transformed into digital artifacts that applications and services can consume, ultimately influencing real-world operations by enabling intelligent automation, predictive maintenance, and efficient resource allocation.

Through this proof of concept, we aim to showcase how the MultiX architecture can serve as a foundation for the next generation of industrial manufacturing, combining sensing and communication into a unified framework that enhances efficiency, resilience, and scalability in industrial environments.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The MultiX approach advances next-generation wireless networks by integrating sensing and communication into a unified framework. By leveraging multi-band, multi-static, multi-sensor, and multi-technology capabilities, MP6R enhances situational awareness, localization, and environmental perception, transforming wireless networks into active sensing platforms that dynamically adapt to their surroundings. This convergence not only improves spectrum efficiency but also unlocks new applications in smart cities, autonomous systems, and industrial automation.

To address network heterogeneity and ensure seamless interoperability, MultiX introduces a novel architecture composed of three key components: the MPS for distributed sensing and data acquisition, the MP6RC for intelligent orchestration and resource allocation, and the DASH for secure, privacy-preserving data management. This modular design enables scalable, real-time decision-making while maintaining robustness across diverse network conditions.

As a proof of concept, the Multi-Layer Digital Twin for Industrial Manufacturing demonstrates how contextual data fusion enhances predictive analytics, optimizes process efficiency, and supports proactive network management in dynamic environments. By continuously synchronizing real-world conditions with virtual models, this approach enables adaptive control strategies that improve reliability and performance.

Future work will focus on MultiX's cross-layer sensing integration, and validating its real-world performance

across multiple use cases. Key challenges include optimizing AI-driven sensor fusion techniques, minimizing latency in perception-aware applications, and addressing security concerns related to distributed data processing. By overcoming these challenges, MultiX will contribute to the evolution of intelligent, perception-driven 6G networks that seamlessly integrate communication and sensing for next-generation connectivity.

REFERENCIAS

- [1] W. Jiang, Q. Zhou, J. He, M. A. Habibi, S. Melnyk, M. El-Absi, B. Han, M. D. Renzo, H. D. Schotten, F.-L. Luo, T. S. El-Bawab, M. Juntti, M. Debbah, and V. C. M. Leung, "Terahertz communications and sensing for 6g and beyond: A comprehensive review," *IEEE Communications Surveys Tutorials*, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 2326–2381, 2024.
- [2] N. González-Prelcic, M. Furkan Keskin, O. Kaltiokallio, M. Valkama, D. Dardari, X. Shen, Y. Shen, M. Bayraktar, and H. Wymeersch, "The integrated sensing and communication revolution for 6g: Vision, techniques, and applications," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 112, no. 7, pp. 676–723, 2024.
- [3] S. Tan, Y. Ren, J. Yang, and Y. Chen, "Commodity WiFi sensing in ten years: Status, challenges, and opportunities," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 9, no. 18, pp. 17 832–17 843, 2022.
- [4] Y. He, Y. Chen, Y. Hu, and B. Zeng, "WiFi Vision: Sensing, recognition, and detection with commodity MIMO-OFDM WiFi," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 7, no. 9, pp. 8296–8317, 2020.
- [5] J. Yang, X. Chen, H. Zou, D. Wang, Q. Xu, and L. Xie, "EfficientFi: Toward large-scale lightweight WiFi sensing via CSI compression," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 9, no. 15, pp. 13 086–13 095, 2022.
- [6] Y. Zeng, D. Wu, J. Xiong, J. Liu, Z. Liu, and D. Zhang, "MultiSense: Enabling multi-person respiration sensing with commodity WiFi," *Proceedings of the ACM on Interactive, Mobile, Wearable and Ubiquitous Technologies*, vol. 4, no. 3, sep 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3411816>
- [7] H. Choi, M. Fujimoto, T. Matsui, S. Misaki, and K. Yasumoto, "Wi-CaL: WiFi sensing and machine learning based device-free crowd counting and localization," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 24 395–24 410, 2022.
- [8] I. Ahmad, A. Ullah, and W. Choi, "WiFi-based human sensing with deep learning: Recent advances, challenges, and opportunities," *IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society*, vol. 5, pp. 3595–3623, 2024.
- [9] T. Wang, Y. Liang, X. Shen, X. Zheng, A. Mahmood, and Q. Z. Sheng, "Edge computing and sensor-cloud: Overview, solutions, and directions," *ACM Comput. Surv.*, vol. 55, no. 13s, Jul. 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3582270>
- [10] Y. Lu, W. Mao, H. Du, O. A. Dobre, D. Niyato, and Z. Ding, "Semantic-aware vision-assisted integrated sensing and communication: Architecture and resource allocation," *IEEE Wireless Communications*, vol. 31, no. 3, pp. 302–308, 2024.
- [11] Multix, "Multix website," 2025, accessed: 2025-02-26. [Online]. Available: <https://multix-6g.eu/>

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